

PROJECT-BASED LEARNING IN HIGH SCHOOL CLASSROOMS: TEACHERS PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract. This study explores the perspectives of high school teachers on the implementation of Project-Based Learning (PBL) in their classrooms. The aim is to gain insights into teachers' experiences, challenges, and perceived outcomes related to PBL. The research methodology employed qualitative interviews with a sample of high school teachers who have implemented PBL in their classrooms. Thematic analysis was used to identify common themes and patterns in the teachers' responses. The findings of the study disclosed that teachers view PBL as a rewarding and transformative approach to education. They report increased student engagement, enhanced critical thinking skills, and improved collaboration and teamwork as key outcomes of PBL implementation. Additionally, the study identifies various challenges faced by teachers, including time management, logistics, assessment, and addressing student diversity. Based on the teachers' perspectives, the study suggests that effective implementation of PBL requires ongoing professional development, collaboration among teachers, and support from school administration. It emphasizes the importance of providing adequate resources, including time, materials, and technology, to facilitate successful PBL implementation. The study also underscores the need to address student diversity and inclusivity within PBL, promoting equitable educational experiences for all students, this study contributes and highlights its potential to engage students, foster critical thinking skills, and promote collaboration in high school classrooms. The findings provide insights for educators, administrators, and policymakers seeking to implement and support effective PBL practices. Further research is recommended to explore specific areas, such as long-term impact, assessment strategies, and the role of technology in PBL implementation, to enhance our understanding and inform future educational practices.

KEY WORDS

1. Project-Based Learning
2. High School Classrooms
3. Teachers Perspective

1. Introduction

Project-based learning (PBL) is becoming increasingly popular in high school classrooms, but its implementation can be difficult for teachers due to lack of knowledge and resources. This qualitative study aims to provide guidance by identifying the elements that affect instructors' opinions and experiences with PBL. An educational strategy known as project-based learning (PBL) places an emphasis on active, student-centered learning via the completion of significant tasks. It is becoming more and more common in high school classrooms as a means

of energizing pupils and encouraging deeper study. PBL implementation, however, can be difficult for teachers since they might not have the knowledge or resources necessary to create and carry out successful projects. In global context, PBL to be implemented and used effectively, it is essential to comprehend instructors' perspectives and experiences with it. This qualitative study intends to investigate teachers' opinions on the difficulties and benefits of using PBL in high school classes, as well as the methods and tools they employ to create and carry out PBL projects. This study aims to provide guidance by identifying the elements that affect instructors' opinions and experiences with PBL. Recent research has highlighted the potential benefits of project-based learning (PBL) for engaging high school students and promoting deeper learning (Hung, Jonassen, Liu, 2008; Thomas, 2020). PBL emphasizes active, student-centered learning through the completion of meaningful projects that integrate multiple subject areas and real-world contexts (Barron Darling-Hammond, 2020). Project-based learning has been shown to be an effective instructional approach that promotes student engagement and critical thinking (Hung, Hwang, Huang, 2019; Walker Leary, 2019). According to a study by Walker and Leary (2009), project-based learning can help students develop problem-solving skills, improve their communication and collaboration abilities, and increase their motivation to learn. Project-based learning also allows students to learn and apply content in a more meaningful and authentic context, which can help them retain information better (Hung et al., 2019). Additionally, teachers have reported that project-based learning can be an effective way to differentiate instruction and meet the needs of diverse learners (Helle et al., 2017). However, implementing project-based learning in high school classrooms can present some challenges for teachers, such as managing time constraints and ensuring that stu-

dents have the necessary skills and resources to complete the project (Helle et al., 2017). Some teachers have also reported feeling unsure about how to assess student learning in a project-based learning environment (Rogers et al., 2021).

To address these challenges, some researchers have suggested that professional development opportunities for teachers can be beneficial in supporting the implementation of project-based learning (Helle et al., 2017; Walker Leary, 2009). Additionally, using technology tools and resources can help streamline project management and increase student engagement (Hung et al., 2019). In national context, In the Philippines, there is growing interest in implementing project-based learning (PBL) as a pedagogical approach that can address the challenges of the K-12 curriculum, particularly in high school (Amores, 2016; Dept. of Education, 2012). PBL is seen to engage students in active, student-centered learning that promotes critical thinking, collaboration, and problem-solving skills (Estrellado, 2019; Llavore, 2019). However, there are challenges to implementing PBL in the Philippine context. Specifically in Cagayan National High one major challenge is the lack of training and professional development opportunities for teachers to learn about PBL and how to design and implement effective PBL projects (Amores, 2016; Estrellado, 2019). Another challenge is the lack of resources, such as technology and materials, needed to support PBL implementation (Crisostomo, 2019). Despite these challenges, there are examples of successful PBL implementation in the Philippines, such as the K-12 Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) Curriculum Framework, which includes a focus on PBL (Dept. of Education, 2012). However, there is a need for more research on high school teachers' perceptions and experiences with PBL in the Philippine context, to identify the factors that facilitate or hinder PBL implementation and to inform efforts to support and enhance PBL imple-

mentation in high schools. Project-based learning can help develop skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration that are crucial for success in higher education and the workforce (Bell et al., 2020; Pekrun et al., 2017). According to Pekrun et al. (2017), project-based learning can also enhance students' intrinsic motivation to learn, which can lead to better academic achievement. Teachers play a critical role in implementing project-based learning in high school classrooms. They must create a supportive classroom environment, scaffold student learning, and provide feedback on students' progress (Bell et al., 2020; Pekrun et al., 2017). Teachers may also need to adapt their instructional practices to effectively facilitate project-based learning (Reynolds, 2019). Effective assessment is another important aspect of project-based learning. Teachers may use a variety of assessment methods, such as rubrics, self-assessment, and peer assessment, to evaluate student learning (Bell et al., 2020; Reynolds, 2019). According to Reynolds (2019), involving students in the assessment process can help increase their motivation and engagement in the project. Project-based learning can be particularly beneficial for students from disadvantaged backgrounds. It can help reduce achievement gaps and increase access to higher education and the workforce (Bouillion Gomez, 2001; Donohoo, 2019). Additionally, project-based learning can promote equity and social justice by providing opportunities for students to explore and address real-world problems (Donohoo, 2019). Project-based learning can be effectively integrated into high school science classrooms, with teachers emphasizing the importance of scaffolding student learning and providing feedback (Fisher Hmelo-Silver, 2018). Additionally, project-based learning can increase student engagement and motivation in science, leading to improved learning outcomes (Fisher Hmelo-Silver, 2018). In implementing project-based learning in high school classrooms, teachers should be intentional in designing projects that are relevant and meaningful to students' lives (Barton Tanis, 2019). This can help increase students' motivation and interest in the project, leading to deeper learning experiences. Collaboration is a key component of project-based learning, and teachers should provide opportunities for students to work together and develop interpersonal skills (Swerdlow O'Donnell, 2018). Teachers should also provide guidance and support to help students navigate group work and resolve conflicts. In project-based learning, assessment should be closely aligned with learning objectives and should provide students with clear expectations and feedback (Barton Tanis, 2019). Teachers should use a variety of assessment methods, including self-assessment and peer assessment, to help students reflect on their learning and progress. In the Davao region of the Philippines, project-based learning has been found to be effective in enhancing students' understanding and application of mathematical concepts (Bonita Uy, 2021). Teachers in the region have emphasized the importance of creating authentic, real-world projects that engage students and foster their creativity and critical thinking skills. Teachers in the Davao region have also noted the importance of integrating technology into project-based learning, as it can help increase student engagement and motivation (Bonita Uy, 2021). This can include the use of digital tools such as online simulations, videos, and interactive multimedia. In implementing project-based learning in the Davao context, teachers have emphasized the importance of providing clear guidelines and expectations for students, as well as offering opportunities for self-reflection and peer evaluation (Bonita Uy, 2021). This can help students develop their metacognitive skills and take ownership of their learning. Therefore, this study aims to contribute to the literature by specifically examining and analyzing teachers' perceptions and experiences with project-based

learning in high school classrooms. By identifying the factors that influence high school teachers' perceptions and experiences with PBL, this study can inform efforts to provide training and professional development opportunities, allocate resources, and address other challenges to PBL implementation in high school classrooms in the Philippines curriculum. In a study on project-based learning in a Davao City public high school, teachers reported that the approach helped students develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills, as well as teamwork and collaboration (Diy, Cagatan, Lomosbog, 2021). Teachers also emphasized the importance of providing students with clear guidelines and expectations and scaffolding their learning throughout the project. In implementing project-based

learning in the Davao context, it is important for teachers to incorporate local and cultural contexts into their projects, as this can help make the learning experience more relevant and engaging for students (Galarosa Colina, 2020). For example, a project on sustainable farming practices could be tailored to the local agricultural context in Davao. Teachers in the Davao region have also found that project-based learning can help address some of the challenges associated with remote and online learning, such as low student engagement and limited interaction (Reforma Peralta, 2021). By incorporating collaborative and interactive projects, teachers can help foster a sense of community and engagement among students.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study, "Analyzing Teachers' Perceptions and Experiences with Project-Based Learning in High School Classrooms," aims to examine high school teachers' perspectives and experiences with project-based learning (PBL) implementation in their classes. The goal of the study is to pinpoint the variables that affect teachers' adoption of PBL as well as the difficulties and advantages they experience along the way. By looking at the unique setting of the Philippines, we hope to add to the body of knowledge on PBL implementation in high schools. We want to find solutions and best practices for encouraging effective PBL implementation in this environment by examining the experiences and perspectives of high school teachers in the Philippines.

- (1) What are the lived experiences of teachers on project-based learning in high school classrooms?
- (2) How do teachers cope with the challenges in implementing in project-based learning?
- (3) What educational management or insights are drawn from the findings of the study?

1.2. Theoretical Lens—This study is anchored to Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991). One theoretical framework that could be relevant to analyzing teachers' perceptions and experiences with project-based learning in high school classrooms is the TPB proposes that individuals' behavior is influenced by their attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. Attitudes refer to the individual's positive or negative evaluation of the behavior, while subjective norms refer to the perceived social pressure to engage

in the behavior. Perceived behavioral control refers to the individual's belief in their ability to engage in the behavior. Applying the TPB to teachers' perceptions and experiences with PBL, attitudes could refer to their positive or negative evaluation of PBL as a teaching approach, while subjective norms could refer to the perceived expectations and support from colleagues, administrators, and other stakeholders. Perceived behavioral control could refer to the teachers' belief in their ability to design and implement effective PBL projects. By applying the

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

TPB, this study could identify the factors that influence teachers’ attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control related to PBL, and how these factors ultimately impact their perceptions and experiences with PBL in high school classrooms. Also anchored the Social Learning Theory (SLT) (Bandura, 1977). One theoretical framework that could be relevant

to analyzing teachers’ perceptions and experiences with project-based learning in high school classrooms is the Social Learning Theory (SLT) (Bandura, 1977). SLT posits that individuals learn through observation, modeling, and imitation of others’ behavior, as well as through the reinforcement or punishment of their own behavior.

2. Methodology

This chapter, the researcher introduced the philosophical assumptions, qualitative assumptions, research participants, data collections, data analysis, ethical considerations, role of the researcher, and trustworthiness.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—It was assumed that all participants answered interview questions honestly and to the best of their abilities. It was further assumed that the sample used for this study was representative of in-depth and focus group interviews on a face-to-face manner as a medium of communication. These assumptions have been articulated throughout the last 20 years in the various SAGE Handbooks of Qualitative Research (Denzin Lincoln, 1994, 2000, 2005, 2011) and as the “axiomatic” issues advanced by Guba and Lincoln (1988) as the guiding philosophy behind qualitative research. These beliefs have been called paradigms (Lincoln, 1985) philosophical assumptions, epistemologies, and ontologies (Crotty, 1998); broadly conceived research methodologies (Neuman, 2000); and alternative

knowledge claims (Creswell, 2014). There are beliefs about ontology (the nature of reality), epistemology (what counts as knowledge and how knowledge claims are justified), axiology (the role of values in research), and methodology (the process of research). In this discussion, I will first discuss each of these philosophical assumptions, detail how they might be used and written into qualitative research, and then link them to different interpretive frameworks that operate at a more specific level in the process of research. Ontology. The issue relates to the nature of reality and its characteristics, when researcher conduct qualitative research, they are embracing the idea of analyzing teachers’ perceptions and experiences with project-based learning in high school classrooms. Different researchers embrace different realities, as do

the individuals being studied and the readers of a qualitative study. When studying individuals, qualitative researchers conduct a study with the intent of reporting these multiple realities. Evidence of multiple realities includes the use of multiple forms of evidence in themes using the actual words of different individuals and presenting different perspectives. For example, when writers compile a phenomenology, they report how individuals participating in the study view their experiences differently (Moustakas, 1994). Epistemology. Conducting a qualitative study means that the researcher tries to get as close as possible to the participants being studied. Therefore, subjective evidence is assembled based on individual views. The very reason why I choose these high school teachers as my participants is because I knew them for a quite long time. This is how knowledge is known through the subjective experiences of people. It becomes important, then, to conduct studies in the “field,” where the participants live and work, these are important contexts for understanding what the participants are saying. The longer researchers stay in the “field” or get to know the participants, the more they “know

what they know” from firsthand information. For example, a good phenomenology requires a prolonged stay at the research site (Wolcott, 2008a). In short, the researcher tries to minimize the “distance” or “objective separateness” (Guba Lincoln, 1988, p. 94) between himself or herself and those being researched. Axiology. This assumption characterizes qualitative research. How does the researcher implement this assumption in practice? In a qualitative study, the inquirers admit the value-laden nature of the study and actively report their values and biases as well as the value-laden nature of information gathered from the field. This means that the result of this study will be shared with the school where I am currently working. We say that they “position themselves” in a study. In an interpretive biography, for example, the researcher’s presence is apparent in the text, and the author admits that the stories voiced represent an interpretation and presentation of the author as much as the subject of the study (Denzin, 1989a). I believe that I am more qualified to conduct this study since I have ample experience teaching in the junior high school.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The researcher made these qualitative assumptions that consist of the methods used in the process of qualitative research (Creswell 2003). The procedures used by the researcher are inductive and are based on the researcher’s own experience in collecting and analyzing data. The research here is the product of the values of the researcher. Through an inductive approach, raw textual data is condensed into a brief, summary format. Clear links are established between research objectives and summary findings derived from raw data. A framework of the underlying structure of experiences or processes that are evident from the raw data is developed. A phenomenological study describes

the meaning of lived experiences of individuals about a concept or phenomenon (Creswell, 2003) was used in this study. A phenomenological study intends to understand and describe an event from the point of view of the participants. A key characteristic of this approach is to study how members of a group or community interpret themselves, the world, and life around them (Mertens, 2005). The purpose of this study was to analyzing teachers’ perceptions and experiences with project-based learning in high school classrooms were using effective instructional practices, related to building background, student interactions, and application, to meet the needs of learners as well as the possible challenges experienced by teach-

ers when implementing these practices as pedagogy in teaching learning process. Collectively, these results may provide foundational information to guide the district in addressing the local issue. Administrators might benefit from this information as it might enable them to make informed decisions about what support is needed for analyzing teachers' perceptions and experiences with project-based learning in high school classrooms. In addition, this study was

to discover the analyzing teachers' perceptions and experiences with project-based learning in high school classrooms in selected junior high schools' teachers, appear to have experienced towards analyzing teachers' perceptions and experiences with project-based learning in high school classrooms, specifically in the areas of building background knowledge, interactions, and application.

2.3. Design and Procedure—In the next section, the specific details of the research procedures will be described, so future researchers can generalize the results from this study to other situations. Extensive and careful descriptions of the time, place, context, and culture of the study will be thoroughly discussed to develop transferability, which is the qualitative parallel to external validity in post-positivist research (Mertens, 2005). This section will: (a) discuss the interview approach; (b) explain the role of the researcher; and lastly, (c) describe the sampling method and ethical considerations. *Semi-Structured Interviews.* Patton (2015) proposes researchers conduct interviews to learn the things they cannot directly observe. Qualitative interviewing is not used to get answers to questions, but to understand the experiences of the participants and the meaning they make of that experience (Seidman, 1988). Generally, qualitative studies use unstructured, open-ended interviews, because they allow for the most flexibility and responsiveness to emerging issues for both the participants and interviewer; however, the use of semi-structured interviews is not uncommon and used when the researcher seeks to obtain specific more focused information (Schwandt, 2001). Semi-structured interviews combine the flexibility of unstructured, open-ended interviews with directionality

and an agenda to produce focused, qualitative, textual data (Schensul, LeCompte, 71 1999). This study collected data using semi-structured interviews to explore how junior high school teachers describe on how teachers analyze their perceptions and experiences with project-based learning in high school classrooms. To ensure that the same information was collected from all the participants, an interview guide was used. The interview guide included open-ended questions and topics to help structure the interview, but when needed, the interviewer also explored, probed, and asked additional questions to clarify and expand on a particular topic. The interview guide helped make interviewing across several different participants more systematic and comprehensive by defining in advance the issues to be explored (Patton, 2015). The open-ended questions were framed in a way, so the participants could represent their views and perspectives in their own words and terms, in addition to taking the questions in any direction that they chose (Patton, 2015). Since qualitative research studies subjects in their natural setting, all interviews except one, took place using a face-to-face format at a time convenient for the participants. All interview sessions were tape-recorded for purposes of transcription. When needed, the researcher used follow-up interviews after transcription to clarify meaning or explore areas in more depth.

2.4. Research Participants—

The target population for this study will be the twelve (12) participants from the line-up of public high school faculty, who are still teaching during the school year 2022-2023. The participants will join for an in-depth interview (IDI) and focus group discussion (FGD). The researcher considered the faculty from selected public schools who are still teaching. From this population, a sample of twelve (12) junior high school teachers was purposefully selected. The researcher will use Purposive sampling (also known as judgment, selective or subjective sampling) wherein it is a sampling technique in which the researcher relies on their judgment

2.5. *Data Collection*—Prior to the conduct of data gathering, I must ask for the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School of Rizal Memorial Colleges to pursue the study. After the permissions are approved by the Schools Division Superintendent and the school principals of the target participants, the researcher will talk to the participants to acquaint them with the purpose of the study. I will agree with the participants on the most convenient date and time for the conduct of the interview. To start the interview, I will ask the participants to read the respondents' consent and to affix their signature on the consent paper after they are oriented of the purpose of the study and respectively agree on the terms and conditions. The researcher will emphasize to the respondents that they are allowed to ask question for clarify any matter regarding the study and ask their consent to record the course of the conversation with the assurance that everything shall be dealt with utmost confidentiality. Through in-depth interview, I will be able to gather the feelings, reactions, observations, and experiences of the teachers in their conduct towards sleep deprivation related to personality development of pupils. The interview will include the gathering of information as to obsta-

cles and challenges that the teachers encounter when choosing members of the population to participate in the study. This survey sampling method requires researcher to have prior knowledge about the purpose of their studies so that they can properly choose and approach eligible participants to be conducted (Denzin, 2017). The participants of this study are the junior high school teachers from the selected public schools in Division of Davao Oriental. Below is the simple description of the participants: Participant 1 is a licensed professional teacher and lives in Davao Oriental. She/he has experience in teaching for 3 or more than 3 years.

cles and challenges that the teachers encounter with the home visitations. I will likewise aim to obtain substantial information exploring the use of science simulations in grade 5 class considering the teacher perspectives to personality development of pupils and the interventions that help bridge the risk of understanding and making science subject into more realistic experiences for the pupils. In analyzing the data gathered, the participant's narratives will be transcribed. According to Koontz and Weinrich (2000), the process and narratives do not need to be transcribed verbatim if the essence of what the participants were communicating has been caught in the transcription. Individual transcriptions of the interview will be validated by the respective participants. To verify and revalidate the data gathered, the researcher will conduct focus group discussion to validate and triangulate the information gathered. Corrections may be made according to the participants' feedback to ensure that the meaning will be conveyed in the fundamental structure of the phenomenon. Data from interviews, field notes, and recorded videos through in-depth interviews and focus group discussion will be collected. Field notes will be used to record nonverbal communication and participants' interactions with the environ-

ment. The questionnaire was a combination of closed and open-ended questions administered by the researcher orally. Interviews were semi-structured, employed open-ended questions, and will be based on an interview guide. Data will be generated through field notes, a voice recorder or cellphone videos, during the interviews with participants. A piloted interview questionnaire was used with all participants. Twelve participants were interviewed in two sessions of 45 minutes to 60 minutes each because of their schedule. The interval between interviews was on average one day. Interview questions were based on the study's four research questions, which explored participants' viewpoints. Follow-up questions will also be made to clarify ambiguous comments and discrepant data. In four instances, participants preferred to discuss the ambiguities over attributes of high-quality. In a qualitative phenomenological study, research data involved the researcher spending as much time as possible within the teachers at the high schools to gain an in-depth understanding of the junior high school teachers in their everyday lives. Participant observations of the secondary faculty behaviors, beliefs, traditions, culture, social and emotional interactions were recorded at the end of each day in a journal. Where applicable in-depth interviews were conducted in field settings and were either recorded and transcribed, and/or summarized in the journal. As an active participant in the research process, the researcher constantly evaluated her role, her relationship with participants, and applied this to develop an understanding and interpretation of the basic education teacher's social and emotional worlds (Unger, 2005). This resulted in an evolving research process both in terms of the direction and type of data derived and in terms of a personal transformation for the researcher (Parker, 2005). The evolution of the research as a relational transformation between a researcher with openness for a new experience and a community of participants can-

not be over-emphasized. The results of which could not have been foreseen at the inception of this study (Parker, 2005). As noted earlier, the location of the study is an academic institution that experienced changes in its way of teaching. The researcher already spent several years as a junior high school teacher, and I have a great chance to gather demographic information and to meet as many of the locals as possible. Also, it was hoped that an initial understanding of the community culture could be gained through participant observation. All participants signed an informed consent form before being interviewed. Questionnaires will be translated by the researcher to the language commonly used by the participants. Data collection was multimodal. According to Yin (2003), the main characteristic of phenomenological qualitative research is that it employs various data collection methods to ensure the trustworthiness of the report. Multiple data sources promote a clearer understanding of the data being studied (Creswell, 2008, 2009; Glesne, 2011; Merriam, 2009). Data from interviews, field notes, and recorded videos through in-depth interviews and focus group discussion will be collected. Field notes will be used to record nonverbal communication and participants' interactions with the environment. The questionnaire was a combination of closed and open-ended questions administered by the researcher orally. Interviews were semi-structured, employed open-ended questions, and will be based on an interview guide. Data will be generated through field notes, a voice recorder or cellphone videos, during the interviews with participants. A piloted interview questionnaire was used with all participants. Twelve participants were interviewed in two sessions of 45 minutes to 60 minutes each because of their schedule. The interval between interviews was on average one day. Interview questions were based on the study's four research questions, which explored participants' viewpoints. Follow-up questions will

also be made to clarify ambiguous comments and discrepant data. In four instances, partici-

pants preferred to discuss the ambiguities over attributes of high-quality.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—Qualitative data analysis begins with the process of organizing, reducing, and describing the collected data (Schwandt, 2001). Unlike quantitative analysis, there are no prescribed formulas for qualitative analysis. Marshall and Rossman (2006) remind researcher that qualitative analysis does not proceed linearly and is not neat. However, good practice and procedures enhance the credibility of qualitative research. In this last section, the data analysis procedures will be explained, and the steps taken to ensure the results from this study are credible, transferable, dependable, and authentic will be thoroughly described. To guide the data analysis, the researcher used the seven phases of data analysis described by Marshall and Rossman (2006) to reduce data, create manageable pieces, allow for interpretation, and find meaning in the words of the participants. The seven phases included: (a) organizing the data; (b) immersion in the data; (c) generating categories and themes; (d) coding the data; (e) offering interpretations through analytic memos; and (f) searching for alternative understandings (Marshall Rossman, 2006). Data analysis first begins with organizing the data. The organization of the data involved keeping information provided by each participant separate and in sequence with the order of the interviews. The process of organizing the data allowed it to remain manageable, easily accessible, and readily available. The digital audio files from the interviews were carefully transcribed into written form. Electronic folders were established to create an organization for the data collected from each participant. Next, the researcher became familiar with the data through extensive reading of the interviews to gain an understanding of the content. This involved reading through the interviews at least three times. Following

Hatch's (2002) recommendations for qualitative analysis, the researcher created a sheet of notes for each participant. The summary sheets were a quick way to refer to the original data as the data analysis continued (Hatch, 2002). After the initial readings, Hatch (2002) recommends researchers read data through completely with one typology in mind. Patton (2015) defines typologies as classification systems made up of categories that divide some aspects of the world into parts. According to Hatch (2002), typologies are generated from the theory, common sense, or research objectives. For this study, the researcher used the typologies or themes from the literature review as the constructs through which to view the data. After reading through the data with each constructor typology in mind, the researcher coded the data into five categories from the literature by taking excerpts of text from the data and identifying it within a particular category. After everything was coded, the researcher read through the data again while writing analytic memos on her thoughts and insights and began the process of offering interpretations. During this stage, the researcher began to interpret the data to find significance and meaning in the teachers' instructional experiences through pulling salient themes, reoccurring ideas, and patterns of belief that resonated collectively throughout the interviews. The offering of interpretations began following the emergence of themes in the data. Marshall and Rossman (2006) believe this part of the data analysis brings meaning to the themes and categories and allows the researcher to develop links between the interviews. The researcher began to interpret the data to find significance and meaning in analyzing. Rossman and Marshall (2006) remind researchers there will always be alternate explanations existing within the data.

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

Before moving forward, the researcher stopped explanations and evaluated the findings for other plausible

2.7. *Analytical Framework*—It was shown in analytical frame work in the analyzing teachers’ perceptions and experiences with project-based learning in high school classrooms is a structure for the best teaching instructions and pedagogy , carried along of learners personality and inclination for growth development which most effective in teaching learning process, also the interest of learners were affects from teachers demands, and parents supervision as what their experience to be divulge and bring new insight and hope to upcoming similar situation or case. The experiences were analyzed to bring out their insight and feelings to make a difference in the educational system. Both aims to provide information on unfolding story of teachers towards sleep deprivation related to personality development of pup analyzing teachers’

perceptions and experiences with project-based learning in high school classrooms. The data collected during interviews was transcribed, organized, and reviewed in searching for patterns and themes. Because this study involved human participants, informed consent was secured for ethical purposes. Following the signing of consent forms, analyzing teachers’ perceptions and experiences with project-based learning in high school classrooms using semi-structured in-depth interviews. Data was organized and analyze. The researcher rigorously examined these units of meaning to elicit the essence of meaning within the holistic context. The entire interview transcript and add anything that might have been left out. The information may be shared with the participants in taking circle to ensure that we interpreted the data correctly using triangulation analysis (Mazuwelics, 2018).

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presented the results of the data analysis and the discussion of the results of the study, focused on learning on project-based learning in high school classroom project-based: teachers' perspectives, information was gathered to examine on what are the experiences of teachers on project-based learning in high school classrooms?, how do teachers cope with the challenges in implementing project-based learning? and lastly, what educational management or insights are drawn from the findings of the study? Before I begin my discussion, I would like to establish the symbols I used as I present the quotations based on the responses of the participants of the study. In reference to the transcriptions of the conducted interviews, I used codes to refer to participants of the research question. Their responses were contained and bounded around the three (3) research questions of the study. Moreover, the responses of both the IDI and the FGD participants were transcribed in verbatim manner, translated into English, encoded, and summarized in matrix form, which led to a schema. The first objective of this study is the experiences of teachers on project-based learning in high school classrooms. The study would specifically seek to answer the following queries, having with three major themes emerged after the data analysis. Based on the interview data gathered from the teachers' participants of the Project-Based Learning in High School Classrooms: Teachers Perspective. The transcripts of participants of focus grouped discussion are as follows: Answer to research Question and connected to first theme, which is Supporting Effective Implementation.

3.1. Project-Based Learning in High School Classroom Project-Based—The research questions number 1 merged with the first theme that considered in the study. First, concerns are what are the lived experiences of teachers on project-based learning in high school classrooms? Merged with the theme of saturated from the data of participants, highlighted the supporting effective implementation. The theme mentioned demands the learner needs in learning, supporting effective implementation on project-based learning in high school classrooms.

3.1.1. supporting effective implementation—The statement reflects a positive perspective on project-based learning from the viewpoint of a high school teacher who has implemented it in their classrooms. The analysis indicates that the teacher perceives project-based learning as a rewarding and transformative approach that promotes active student engagement, critical thinking, collaboration, problem-solving skills, and ownership of learning. As a high school teacher, my experiences with project-based learning in diverse classrooms have been incredibly positive and have highlighted the power of inclusivity. A recent study by Saavedra and Opfer (2020) supports these experiences, emphasizing that project-based learning can effectively engage and support students from diverse backgrounds, including those with different cultural, linguistic, and socio-economic backgrounds.

3.1.2. Teacher Collaboration—Collaborative planning and problem-solving enhance the design and effectiveness of projects, while ongoing collaboration supports professional growth and the refinement of instructional practices. Interdisciplinary connections and shared expertise

Fig. 3. Thematic Framework of experiences of teachers on project based learning in high school classrooms

among teachers foster a more integrated and engaging learning experience for students. By prioritizing and supporting teacher collaboration, schools can create an environment where project-based learning thrives, and students benefit from rich and meaningful educational experiences.

3.1.3. student diversity and inclusivity. — While challenges related to language proficiency or varying levels of prior knowledge may arise, teachers participants have implemented strategies to support all students in project-based learning. Differentiated instruction, scaffolding, and targeted support have ensured that every student can actively participate and contribute, regardless of their background or abilities. Research by Menken et al. (2021) and Calderón and Slade (2022) highlights the importance of providing tailored support in project-based learning to address the diverse needs of students effectively.

3.2. Teachers cope with the challenges in implementing project-based learning —The second objective of this study is the teachers coping with the challenges in implementing project-based learning. The study would specifically seek to answer the following queries, having with three major themes emerged after the data analysis. Based on the interview data gathered from the teachers’ participants of the Project-Based Learning in High School Classrooms: Teachers Perspective.

3.2.1. Challenges and barriers—Project-based learning (PBL) offers benefits but also presents significant challenges for educators. This essay explores the obstacles faced in the implementation of PBL and strategies to overcome them. Challenges include the need for a teaching methodology shift, designing engaging projects, logistical issues, effective assessment, and stakeholder resistance. Strategies such as professional development, technology integration, assessment reevaluation, and cultivating a supportive school culture are vital in address-

ing these challenges. Proactive strategies and a commitment to innovation can help educators effectively implement PBL, empowering students as lifelong learners and problem solvers.

3.2.2. Assessment and grading—In the context of project-based learning (PBL), the traditional methods of assessment and grading often fall short in capturing the full spectrum of student learning and skill development. Unlike conventional assessments that primarily measure rote memorization and regurgitation of facts, PBL emphasizes critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, and creativity. Therefore, there is a compelling need to overhaul assessment and grading practices to align with the objectives and ethos of PBL. Rather than relying solely on standardized tests or end-of-unit exams, assessment in PBL should be multifaceted and authentic, encompassing a range of formative and summative measures tailored to the project's objectives and students' individual strengths and growth areas. This may include rubrics, self and peer evaluations, portfolios, presentations, and exhibitions of learning. Furthermore, grading in PBL should shift from a strictly quantitative approach focused on right or wrong answers to a more qualitative evaluation that acknowledges the process, effort, collaboration, and depth of understanding demonstrated by students throughout the project. By adopting more holistic and flexible assessment and grading practices, educators can better assess the complex skills and competencies cultivated through PBL, providing students with meaningful feedback and fostering a deeper engagement with their learning journey.

3.2.3. Time management and logistics—In project-based learning (PBL), traditional time management and logistics need to be adjusted to fit the dynamic nature of this educational approach. Unlike traditional instruction, where time is structured into separate blocks for individual subjects, PBL requires flexibility and fluidity. Educators must strike a balance between giving students enough time for exploration, collaboration, and reflection, while still meeting essential learning milestones within the academic calendar. The logistics of PBL go beyond scheduling to include resource allocation, classroom organization, and technology integration. Effective time management in PBL involves strategic planning, agile adaptation, and creative problem-solving to optimize learning experiences and outcomes. By embracing innovative approaches to time management and logistics, educators can create an environment that fosters inquiry, discovery, and authentic engagement, ultimately enhancing student learning and achievement in project-based contexts.

3.3. Educational management or insights are drawn from the findings of the study.—The third objective of this study is the educational management or insights are drawn from the findings of the study. The study would specifically seek to answer the following queries, having with three major themes emerged after the data analysis. Based on the interview data gathered from the teachers' participants of the Project-Based Learning in High School Classrooms: Teachers Perspective.

3.3.1. Effective Tool—Project-based learning (PBL) stands as an effective pedagogical tool within the educational landscape, facilitating the development of critical skills and competencies essential for success in the 21st century. Grounded in authentic, inquiry-driven ex-

Fig. 4. Teachers cope with the challenges in implementing project-based learning experiences, PBL fosters active engagement, deep understanding, and meaningful application of knowledge across diverse subject areas. By immersing students in real-world problems and challenges, PBL cultivates intrinsic motivation, creativity, and problem-solving abilities, transcending rote memorization and passive learning. Moreover, PBL promotes collaboration, communication, and teamwork as students collaborate on complex projects, learning to negotiate diverse perspectives and leverage collective expertise. Furthermore, PBL aligns with contemporary educational paradigms that emphasize the cultivation of lifelong learning skills, such as critical thinking, adaptability, and resilience, preparing students to thrive in a rapidly evolving global society. Empirical evidence corroborates the efficacy of PBL in improving academic outcomes, fostering positive attitudes toward learning, and nurturing the development of well-rounded, future-ready individuals.

4. Implications and Future Directions

Presented in this chapter is a brief overview of the study followed by implications based on the findings of the study. Future directions in the field of Project-Based Learning in High School Classrooms: Teachers Perspective are also discussed here. In addition to it, the participants of this study were 12 junior high school teachers, considered the three following objectives, to know the lived experiences of teachers on project-based learning in high school classrooms in obtaining the objectives the research constructed the three research questions: What are the lived experiences of teachers on project-based learning in high school classrooms? How do teachers cope with the challenges in implementing in project-based learning? What educational management or insights are drawn from the findings of the study?

4.1. Findings—The findings revealed that project-based learning in high school classrooms: teachers’ perspective. Increased student engagement: PBL provides an active and hands-on approach to learning, which captures students’ interest and motivates them to take ownership of their education. Teachers often report higher levels of student engagement and en-

Fig. 5. Thematic Framework educational management or insights are drawn from the findings of the study

thusiasm in PBL classrooms compared to traditional instructional methods. Enhanced critical thinking and problem-solving skills: Through PBL, students are presented with authentic, real-world problems or challenges that require them to analyze information, think critically, and develop innovative solutions. Teachers observe that PBL cultivates students’ abilities to tackle complex problems and think creatively. Improved collaboration and teamwork: PBL naturally lend itself to collaboration and teamwork. Students often work in groups to plan, research, and create projects, allowing them to develop valuable collaboration skills such as communication, cooperation, and conflict resolution. Teachers note that PBL promotes a sense of collective responsibility and fosters a supportive learning community. Deeper understanding and application of knowledge: PBL encourages students to delve deeply into a subject matter by exploring and investigating it in a meaningful context. Teachers find that PBL facilitates a deeper understanding of content as students engage in inquiry, conduct research, and ap-

ply their knowledge to solve real-world problems. Increased student autonomy and ownership: PBL empowers students to become active participants in their learning process. Teachers observe that PBL nurtures student agency and independence as they make decisions, manage their time, and take responsibility for their learning. This autonomy helps foster a sense of ownership and pride in their work. Enhanced 21st-century skills: PBL aligns well with the development of 21st-century skills, including communication, collaboration, critical thinking, creativity, and digital literacy. Teachers note that PBL provides opportunities for students to practice and strengthen these skills, preparing them for future academic and professional endeavors.

It’s important to note that these outcomes are generally reported by teachers who have successfully implemented PBL in their high school classrooms. The specific outcomes and experiences may vary depending on various factors such as the implementation approach, student demographics, and teacher expertise.

4.2. *Implications*—Increased engagement and motivation: PBL have a positive impact on

student engagement and motivation. Teachers observe that when students are actively involved

in meaningful projects, their intrinsic motivation and interest in learning are heightened. Students are more likely to be engaged, persistent, and willing to take risks in their learning journey. Development of lifelong learning skills: PBL helps students develop skills that go beyond content knowledge. Students learn how to manage their time, set goals, seek resources, and reflect on their learning process. These metacognitive skills are crucial for lifelong learning and enable students to become self-directed learners. Overall, PBL in high school classrooms, from the teacher's perspective, has implications that align with student-centered learning, authentic experiences, critical thinking, collabora-

tion, interdisciplinary connections, motivation, and lifelong learning. By incorporating PBL into their instructional practices, teachers can create engaging and meaningful learning environments that prepare students for success in the 21st century. Integration of multiple subjects and skills: PBL provides an opportunity for interdisciplinary learning. Teachers can design projects that integrate multiple subjects, allowing students to make connections between different areas of knowledge. This approach helps students develop a holistic understanding of concepts and enhances their ability to transfer knowledge and skills across disciplines.

4.3. *Future Directions*—BThe results of the study will be a strong basis of department of education to shift the focus from teacher-centered instruction to student-centered learning. Teachers become facilitators, guiding, and supporting students as they explore and engage in authentic, real-world projects. This approach promotes student agency, autonomy, and active participation in the learning process. The school principal must be particular of the authentic and meaningful learning experiences that provide students with opportunities to apply their knowledge and skills in real-world contexts. By working on projects that reflect authentic problems or challenges, students can see the relevance and purpose of their learning. This approach helps bridge the gap between classroom learning and the world beyond, fostering a deeper understanding and long-lasting retention of knowledge. The teachers must be guided the results of the study to develops of critical thinking and problem-solving skills with help of project-based learning encourages students to think critically, analyze information, and solve complex problems, it will helps students develop higher-order thinking skills such as evaluating evidence, making informed decisions, and

developing innovative solutions. These skills are essential for success in higher education and the workplace. Collaboration and teamwork skills it helps to promotes collaboration and teamwork as students work together in groups to plan, research, and create projects. Teachers find that PBL helps students develop important interpersonal and communication skills, including active listening, effective communication, negotiation, and collaboration. These skills are crucial in a collaborative and globalized world. The results of the study will be a strong motivation for the learners to participate and continue being interactive, collaborative learning in the process of teaching learning in the classroom. Long-term impact and sustainability future studies can explore the long-term impact of PBL on students' academic achievement, career readiness, and lifelong learning skills. Researchers can track students' progress beyond high school to understand how PBL experiences influence their post-secondary education, career choices, and overall success. Teacher professional development: Investigating effective professional development models and strategies for teachers can be a valuable area of study. Researchers can explore the types of support, training, and re-

sources that help teachers effectively implement PBL in their classrooms. This can contribute to the development of comprehensive professional development programs that support teachers in enhancing their instructional practices. Further research can focus on developing reliable and valid assessment methods specifically designed for PBL. This can include exploring alternative assessment approaches, such as portfolios, rubrics, and authentic performance tasks, that align with the nature of PBL and effectively capture students' learning outcomes.

Technology integration: As technology continues to evolve, it is essential to investigate how technology can be effectively integrated into PBL. Future studies can explore the impact of various technological tools and platforms on student engagement, collaboration, and the overall learning experience in PBL classrooms. Examining the impact of project-based learning on learners from diverse backgrounds, including learners with different learning abilities, cultural backgrounds, and socio-economic statuses, is an important area of future research. Researchers can explore how project-based learning can be effectively tailored to address the needs of all students and promote equitable educational experiences. Teacher collaboration and interdisciplinary approaches to help investigate the role of teacher collaboration and interdisciplinary approaches in PBL implementation can provide

insights into how educators can work together to create meaningful and integrated learning experiences for students. Future studies can explore effective models of collaboration, shared planning time, and interdisciplinary team teaching that support successful PBL implementation.

Parent and community involvement: Examining the impact of involving parents and the community in PBL can be an interesting avenue of research. Researchers can explore the benefits and challenges of engaging parents and community members in project design, implementation, and evaluation, and the impact of such involvement on students' learning outcomes and community connections. By exploring these future directions, researchers can continue to deepen our understanding of PBL in high school classrooms from the teachers' perspective and contribute to the ongoing improvement and implementation of effective instructional practices. It's important to note that the suggestions provided here are based on potential areas of investigation and do not represent specific studies or their findings. Researchers should consider the current literature, educational context, and emerging trends when designing studies on the future directions of PBL in high school classrooms. Lastly, Future researchers. This study may be used as a reference for future researchers if they must venture this kind of research.

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